

Geology Guided Spatial Temporal Frailty Models for Volcanic Eruption Prediction

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Abstract

Volcano eruption prediction remains a major challenge due to sparse historical data and complex geological patterns. This paper explores the application of survival analysis—a statistical method for predicting time-to-event outcomes—to this domain from a global perspective. We propose a survival model that integrates volcano features, eruption history, and geological relationships. To handle the high-dimensional feature space while maintaining interpretability, we employed dimensionality reduction techniques, specifically Nonnegative Matrix Factorization (NMF) and Partial Least Squares (PLS).

Proposed models were evaluated on a large dataset containing over 10,000 eruptions from more than 900 volcanoes. Under standard evaluation metrics, our methods improve over a penalized Andersen–Gill baseline and are often competitive with Random Survival Forests, while remaining interpretable. NMF and PLS help extract key risk factors and yield a compact model.

Our main contribution lies in introducing a novel and interpretable survival analysis framework for global volcanic eruption risk assessment. It provides a statistically grounded way to rank high-risk volcanoes for long-term forecasting and offers a clear basis for further spatial and temporal extensions.

Key Words: Survival analysis, spatial data analysis, frailty model, Nonnegative matrix factorization

1. Introduction

Accurately predicting volcanic eruptions is crucial for mitigating risks to human life, infrastructure, and ecosystems, especially in densely populated or economically important regions near active volcanoes. However, volcanic activity is irregular and varies across space and time, which makes simple rules or fixed thresholds insufficient. To address this, researchers have explored a range of statistical and machine learning methods using historical eruption sequences and multi-source monitoring data. Existing methods can be grouped into four main categories: (1) point process models, (2) state-space and Markov models, (3) Bayesian methods combined with expert systems, and (4) general machine learning methods, each with specific focus and limitations.

Point process models aim to capture the timing and recurrence of eruption events. The simplest is the Poisson process, which assumes a constant average rate and independence between events, and can work for volcanoes with regular activity [3]. Many volcanoes are more complex, so extensions are used. The Weibull process can model time-varying rates [3, 9]. When self-triggering occurs, where a larger eruption increases short-term activity, the Hawkes process is appropriate [3]. These models are mathematically convenient but rely on specific assumptions, and they allow only limited incorporation of covariates.

Volcanic systems often switch between latent phases such as quiescence and eruptive activity. State-space models and Markov processes capture these dynamics by modeling eruptions as state-dependent with transitions governed by latent regimes. Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) have been used to infer phases from historical records, revealing long dormant periods with intermittent activity [13]. Recent work proposes simplified two-state Markov models that alternate between “low activity” and “eruptive” states, estimating eruption rates and transition probabilities jointly [14].

Bayesian methods and expert systems integrate multi-source data and expert judgment, which is useful when observations are sparse or uncertain. Bayesian Networks (BNs) represent conditional dependencies among variables in a directed acyclic graph and have supported real-time decisions at Mt. Ruapehu and Whakaari under limited data [4]. Rule-based expert systems encode monitoring heuristics, and many have probabilistic upgrades such as the Bayesian Event Tree (BET) [12]. Despite dependence on priors, these approaches are transparent, adaptable, and important in operational hazard assessment.

With increasing monitoring data and computation, machine learning (ML) methods have gained attention. Recent studies use deep learning to model temporal patterns in monitoring data. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), including LSTMs, classify seismic waveforms and forecast eruptions from sequences [11]. Cross-volcano transfer learning with satellite and ground observations achieved average AUC over 0.8 up to 12 weeks ahead [2]. Other studies report conserved seismic and degassing precursors, suggesting the feasibility of generalized models. A general-purpose ML model trained on Mount St. Helens and other volcanoes reached 95% short-term forecasting accuracy [10]. These results indicate that ML can extract transferable eruption signals and improve early warning in data-limited settings. However, interpretability remains a common limitation for these models.

Apart from the above, most existing models focus on specific volcanoes or regions and may perform well locally. There is relatively little work on long-term, global-scale risk estimation, especially for volcanoes with limited data. This motivates us to explore a unified framework that combine complementary strengths and support global, long-term forecasting across many volcanoes.

Building on these observations, we apply survival analysis to the problem of volcanic hazard assessment. Survival models are designed for time-to-event data and naturally handle censoring and time-varying covariates. In particular, the Cox model estimates instantaneous eruption risk while accommodating spatial and other features.

Our main contributions are as follows: (i) We adapt recurrent-event Cox models with spatial components for global eruption risk; these models handle censoring explicitly and treat eruption-free intervals as informative rather than missing. (ii) We reduce high-cardinality covariates using Nonnegative Matrix Factorization (NMF)/Partial Least Squares (PLS) for a compact, interpretable design. (iii) On a time-ordered split, our variants improve over a penalized Andersen-Gill baseline and are competitive with Random Survival Forest(RSF), clarifying when simple linear structure plus spatial terms can be effective.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews extended models for recurrent event data and relevant dimension reduction techniques used in our method. Section 3 introduces the dataset and presents an exploratory analysis. Section 4 describes three proposed models. Section 5 outlines the experimental design and presents results, including performance comparisons. Section 6 concludes and discusses future work.

2. Preliminaries

In this section we review two Cox Proportional Hazard extensions for recurrent events and briefly summarizes two dimension reduction methods used in our methods.

2.1 Extended Cox models for recurrent events

The standard Cox model [5] assumes one failure time per subject, which is unsuitable for repeated eruptions. Therefore, we look into two extensions.

2.1.1 Andersen-Gill(AG) model

The Andersen–Gill (AG) model [1] treats recurrent events as a single counting process with a shared baseline hazard, without conditioning on the number or timing of prior events or stratifying by event order. It assumes conditional independence given covariates, so within-subject correlation and order effects are ignored. The hazard for subject i is:

$$h_i(t | \mathbf{x}_i(t)) = h_0(t) \cdot \exp(\mathbf{x}_i(t)^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i(t)$ is the covariate vector for subject i at time t , and $h_0(t)$ is the shared baseline hazard across all events.

Estimation is performed via optimizing partial likelihood function:

$$L(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^{N_i} \frac{\exp(\mathbf{x}_i(t_{ij})^\top \boldsymbol{\beta})}{\sum_{\ell \in R(t_{ij})} \exp(\mathbf{x}_\ell(t_{ij})^\top \boldsymbol{\beta})}, \quad (2)$$

where N_i is the number of events for subject i , t_{ij} is the time of the j -th event, and $R(t_{ij})$ denotes the risk set just before t_{ij} .

2.1.2 Cox Proportional Hazards with frailty

The Cox frailty model [16] adds a subject-specific random effect (frailty) to capture unobserved heterogeneity and to induce within-subject correlation of recurrent events, thus addressing the AG model’s independence assumption. It requires a choice of frailty distribution (*e.g.*, Gamma or log-normal), and inference integrates over the latent effect, which raises computational cost and may be sensitive to misspecification. The hazard for subject i in frailty model is:

$$h_i(t | \mathbf{x}_i, v_i) = h_0(t) \exp(\mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i), \quad (3)$$

where $h_0(t)$ is the baseline hazard, and v_i represents a random effect. The frailty v_i is usually modeled as a latent variable. Given observed covariates and pre-specified distributions of frailty, the corresponding likelihood function of Cox frailty model is:

$$L(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^N \int_0^\infty \left[\left(\prod_{j=1}^{n_i} h_i(t_{ij} | \mathbf{x}_i, v_i) \right) \exp \left(- \int_0^{T_i} h_i(u | \mathbf{x}_i, v_i) du \right) \right] p(v_i | \theta) dv_i \quad (4)$$

where $p(v_i | \theta)$ is the frailty density and θ its variance parameter., and n_i is the number of events for subject i .

2.2 Dimension reduction techniques

We explore both unsupervised and supervised dimension reduction techniques.

2.2.1 Nonnegative Matrix Factorization(NMF)

For unsupervised dimension reduction, we look into Nonnegative Matrix Factorization(NMF). In [8], NMF is used to approximate the input matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n \times p}$ by the product of two lower-rank non-negative matrices $W \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n \times k}$ and $H \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{k \times p}$, where $k \ll \min(n, p)$. A key modeling decision is the choice of loss function used to fit the factorization. We consider the following widely used objective for its computational efficiency:

$$\text{Frobenius loss: } \min_{W, H \geq 0} \|X - WH\|_F^2. \quad (5)$$

2.2.2 Partial Least Squares (PLS)

Given a predictor matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ and a response vector $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, partial least squares (PLS) [6] finds a low-dimensional score matrix $T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ (with $r \ll p$), along with loading matrices $P \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times r}$ and $q \in \mathbb{R}^r$. These components are obtained by jointly approximating the predictors and the response, so that $X \approx TP^T$ and $y \approx Tq$.

Formally, we estimate (T, P, q) by solving

$$\min_{T, P, q} \|X - TP^T\|_F^2 + \alpha \|y - Tq\|_2^2 \quad \text{subject to} \quad T^T T = I_r. \quad (6)$$

This objective balances reconstruction of the predictor space (the term $\|X - TP^T\|_F^2$) and agreement with the response (the term $\|y - Tq\|_2^2$), which is useful in high-dimensional settings. In implementation, we use the gap time between eruptions as the response y .

3. Motivating Datasets and Feature Engineering

3.1 Data description

The dataset used in this study was obtained from the Smithsonian Institution’s Global Volcanism Program (GVP) [17], a comprehensive repository documenting volcanic activity worldwide over the past 10,000 years.

We combine two datasets from the GVP: (i) eruption records with dates, VEI, and volcano identifiers; and (ii) static volcano attributes for 957 volcanoes, including coordinates, elevation, type, tectonic setting, population exposure within 5–100 km, etc. We join them by the unique volcano ID.

Figure 1 visualizes global eruption distribution from GVP data, where color represents the maximum VEI (blue for smaller and red–purple for larger eruptions), and circle size indicates nearby population density. High-risk clusters are visible along the Pacific Ring of Fire, particularly in the Americas, Southeast Asia, Japan, and Hawaii. This pattern highlights that eruption impact depends not only on magnitude but also on spatial and demographic context.

Figure 1: Global volcano eruption distribution by VEI and population

3.2 Exploratory data analysis and feature engineering

The dataset exhibits several notable characteristics that influence modeling choices and preprocessing strategies:

Temporal imbalance: Figure 2 plots yearly eruption counts from 0 CE to 2020 CE. The solid teal line (all eruptions) and the dashed red line (VEI ≥ 3 eruptions) both stay near zero until about 1800. After that point the total count climbs sharply, reaching almost 40 eruptions per year by the early 2000s, while the VEI ≥ 3 series rises more slowly and stays below 10. This pattern is highly right-skewed, indicating that many early-period counts are likely under-reported, and thus poses challenges for the train–test split. Because of this temporal bias, we limit our modelling dataset to eruptions recorded after 1800.

Figure 2: Volcanic Eruption Distribution

Spatial heterogeneity: Figure 3 shows the number of eruption records per volcano in the dataset. More than half have fewer than 10 documented eruptions, while a small subset—such as Etna, Aso, and Villarrica—record over 100, with some exceeding 200. The dataset is therefore dominated by a few very active systems. Focusing only on these sites is risky, because sudden eruptions from quiet ones may cause even greater damage, and there are historical cases of that. This spatial imbalance makes it hard to train models that generalize well across all volcanoes, and highlights the need for methods that can work with sparse and uneven data.

Figure 3: Spatial heterogeneity of eruptions

High-cardinality categorical variables: The dataset combines continuous and categorical features, with categorical ones such as volcano type and tectonic settings being the majority. Many

of these fields have more than 10 levels (Figure 4), and some follow a hierarchical tree structure. One-hot encoding therefore yields a high-dimensional, sparse matrix that increases computational cost and the risk of overfitting. To manage this, we apply dimension reduction techniques like NMF and PLS, which suits the non-negative one-hot inputs and provides interpretable low-rank factors for downstream models.

Figure 4: Levels of categorical variables

Handling spatial information: Longitude and latitude have nonlinear spatial effects, we do not use raw coordinates. We instead compute a kernel density estimate (KDE) over historical eruption locations and include the resulting intensity surface as a spatial covariate (Figure 5). This approach allows us to infer high-risk regions based on historical eruption distributions.

Figure 5: Kernel density estimation

4. Methodology

4.1 Proposed hybrid models

We propose three models for estimating the hazard risk of recurrent volcanic eruptions. For all three models, we use NMF and PLS to reduce the dimensionality of non-spatial covariates. While the non-spatial features are processed in a unified way, each model adopts a different strategy to incorporate and process the spatial coordinates.

4.1.1 Andersen–Gill model with KDE

We begin with a baseline Andersen-Gill that uses KDE to incorporate spatial information, calculated from the longitude and latitude of each volcano’s location s_i . This KDE term provides a smoothed measure of eruption intensity in the surrounding region, thereby serving as a spatial covariate in the hazard function:

$$\text{KDE model: } h_i(t|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i) = h_0(t) \exp([\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i, k(s_i)]^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}) \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i$ is the low-dimensional covariate vector obtained by NMF or PLS for volcano i , and $k(s_i)$ is the KDE evaluated at s_i .

4.1.2 CoxPH model with spatial frailty

To account for unobserved spatial heterogeneity that may influence eruption recurrence, we extend the AG model by introducing a spatial frailty term modeled as a Gaussian process (GP). This model captures latent spatial correlations that are not directly explained by observed covariates. The hazard function is formulated as:

$$\text{Frailty model: } h_i(t|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i) = h_0(t) \cdot \exp(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} + v(s_i)), \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i$ is the low-dimensional covariate vector obtained using NMF or PLS for volcano i . The spatial frailty is modeled as a Gaussian process with zero mean and covariance $\Sigma_\theta(\cdot, \cdot)$:

$$v(\cdot) \sim \mathcal{GP}(0, \Sigma_\theta(\cdot, \cdot)), \quad \Sigma_\theta(s_i, s_j) = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\|s_i - s_j\|^2}{2\ell^2}\right), \quad (9)$$

where $\theta = (\sigma^2, \ell)$, $\sigma^2 > 0$, $\ell > 0$, and $\Sigma_\theta(\cdot, \cdot)$ captures spatial correlation between sites.

4.1.3 Cox model with self-exciting component

In addition to spatial dependencies, volcanic eruptions often exhibit short-term clustering, where an eruption increases the probability of subsequent eruptions in the near future. To capture this time-dynamic behavior, we introduce a self-exciting component into the Cox model, allowing past eruption events to influence the hazard function dynamically. The modified hazard function is given by:

$$\text{SE model: } h_i(t|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i) = h_0(t) \cdot \exp(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} + v(s_i) + \gamma \cdot S_i(t)), \quad (10)$$

where $S_i(t) = \sum_{t_j < t} \exp(-\eta(t - t_j))$ encodes self-excitation effects at time t for volcano i , which accumulates the decayed influence of past eruptions. Here γ controls the impact of the self-excitation term on the log-hazard, and η determines the exponential decay rate of past eruption influence.

4.2 Estimation procedure

The estimation procedure is done via penalized partial likelihood. Recall that in model (8), the spatial frailty term v is assumed to follow a Gaussian process:

$$\mathbf{v} = [v(s_1), \dots, v(s_n)]^\top \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma(\theta)), \quad (11)$$

where $\Sigma(\theta)$ is the covariance matrix induced by a kernel $\kappa(s_i, s_j; \theta)$, with θ denoting hyperparameters such as range and variance.

4.2.1 Penalized partial likelihood estimation

For a counting-process or standard Cox setup with event times t_1, \dots, t_K , where i_k denotes the subject failing at time t_k and $R(t_k)$ is the risk set, the partial likelihood is:

$$L_{\text{partial}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{v}) = \prod_{k=1}^K \frac{\exp(x_{i_k}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} + v(s_{i_k}))}{\sum_{j \in R(t_k)} \exp(x_j^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} + v(s_j))}. \quad (12)$$

Since $\mathbf{v} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma(\theta))$, the prior introduces a penalty term in the log-likelihood:

$$\text{penalty}(\mathbf{v}, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{v}^\top \Sigma(\theta)^{-1} \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{2} \log |\Sigma(\theta)|, \quad (13)$$

where the first term penalizes large deviations in \mathbf{v} , and the second term arises when estimating θ , reflecting the determinant of $\Sigma(\theta)$.

The penalized log-likelihood function to be maximized is:

$$\ell_{\text{pen}}(\beta, \mathbf{v}, \theta) = \log L_{\text{partial}}(\beta, \mathbf{v}) - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{v}^\top \Sigma(\theta)^{-1} \mathbf{v} - \frac{1}{2} \log |\Sigma(\theta)|. \quad (14)$$

Our goal is to estimate $\hat{\beta}$, $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$, and $\hat{\theta}$ that maximize $\ell_{\text{pen}}(\beta, \mathbf{v}, \theta)$. Since θ appears in $\Sigma(\theta)$, and \mathbf{v} is an n -dimensional vector, we typically use a block-coordinate or Newton-type method and iterate until convergence.

1. Update \mathbf{v} and β

- Fix θ , then optimize ℓ_{pen} with respect to \mathbf{v} and β .
- Gradient w.r.t. \mathbf{v} :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{v}} \ell_{\text{pen}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{v}} \log L_{\text{partial}}(\beta, \mathbf{v}) - \Sigma(\theta)^{-1} \mathbf{v}. \quad (15)$$

- Gradient w.r.t. β :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \log L_{\text{partial}} = \sum_{k=1}^K \left[x_{i_k} - \frac{\sum_{j \in R(t_k)} x_j \exp\{x_j^\top \beta + v_j\}}{\sum_{j \in R(t_k)} \exp\{x_j^\top \beta + v_j\}} \right]. \quad (16)$$

2. Update θ

- Fix β and \mathbf{v} .
- Optimize ℓ_{pen} w.r.t. θ , using:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left[-\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{v}^\top \Sigma(\theta)^{-1} \mathbf{v} - \frac{1}{2} \log |\Sigma(\theta)| \right]. \quad (17)$$

5. Experiments

5.1 Experimental setup

This section covers the experiment details, benchmark implementations, and a final performance comparison of our proposed models against the benchmarks.

Handling incomplete dates. When a calendar field is partially missing, we impute the earliest plausible value instead of discarding the record. Concretely, an absent `start_month` or `start_day` is set to be 1, while a missing `end_month` or `end_day` is set to be 12 and 28, respectively. This decision may introduce mild temporal bias, but we think for natural disaster prediction this impact is expected to be minor.

Constructing the censoring indicator. We fix the study ending time at $\tau = 01 - 01 - 2021$ and list every documented eruption prior to τ . For each volcano the events partition time into intervals $(\text{start}_j, \text{stop}_j, \delta_j)$, where $\delta_j = 1$ if an eruption closes the interval and $\delta_j = 0$ otherwise. After the last observed eruption we append one additional interval ending at τ ; this final record is always right-censored with $\delta = 0$.

5.1.1 Train test split

Recall that our dataset has a clear time-based pattern, with far more eruptions recorded recently than in the past. A standard random split is inappropriate here because it risks data leakage, where future information could unfairly influence the model during training. To solve this, we split the data chronologically. The dataset is partitioned as follows, using the year 2000 as the cutoff:

- **Train:** 1800 – 1999.
- **Test:** 2000–2020.

This method ensures the model is trained on historical data and tested on more recent events, respecting the natural order of time.

5.2 Benchmark implementations

In order to evaluate the performance of proposed models, we also implement some benchmark models for comparison.

Penalized AG. We use a counting-process Cox model with KDE in place of raw coordinates, one-hot encoded categorical variables, and standardized numeric features. A small ℓ_2 penalty ($\lambda = 0.1$) improves convergence in the high-dimensional design matrix. We optimize the following penalized partial log-likelihood function:

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \left(\mathbf{x}_{AG,ij}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} - \log \sum_{k \in R(t_{ij})} \exp(\mathbf{x}_{AG,kj}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}) \right) - \lambda \|\boldsymbol{\beta}\|_2^2. \quad (18)$$

Elastic-net Cox (EN-Cox). Elastic Net Cox (EN-Cox) model [18, 15] introduces a combined ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 penalty to the Cox partial likelihood, balancing variable selection and coefficient shrinkage. Following these works, we maximize

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \left(\mathbf{x}_{AG,ij}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} - \log \sum_{k \in R(t_{ij})} \exp(\mathbf{x}_{AG,kj}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}) \right) - \lambda \left(\alpha \|\boldsymbol{\beta}\|_1 + \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \|\boldsymbol{\beta}\|_2^2 \right), \quad (19)$$

using the same covariates as the penalized AG. We set $\alpha = 0.8$ and choose λ by five-fold cross-validation on the C-index, giving a sparse yet interpretable model.

Random Survival Forest (RSF). We adopt the ensemble method of [7], because it captures non-linear effects and interactions without parametric assumptions. The estimated cumulative hazard for covariates \mathbf{X} is:

$$\hat{H}(t | \mathbf{X}) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \hat{H}_m(t | \mathbf{X}), \quad (20)$$

where each \hat{H}_m comes from one tree. To implement the RSF model, we first prepared the training data by combining categorical and numerical features into a unified design matrix. The target survival outcome was constructed using event indicators and observed times, following the structured format required by RSF.

5.3 Evaluation criteria and results

To assess the performances of our models and benchmarks, we employ three key evaluation metrics: the Concordance Index (C-index), Integrated Brier Score (IBS), and present a monthly risk map for worldwide volcanoes.

5.3.1 Concordance Index (C-index)

The Concordance Index (C-index) is a widely used metric for evaluating the predictive performance of survival models. It measures the model’s ability to correctly rank pairs of observations in terms of their predicted risk. A C-index of 1.0 indicates perfect concordance between predicted and actual event orderings, while a value of 0.5 corresponds to random guessing. Usually a C-index above 0.7 is often considered good in survival analysis.

Given two volcanoes i and j with observed survival times T_i and T_j , and predicted hazards \hat{h}_i and \hat{h}_j , the C-index is defined as:

$$C = \frac{\sum_{i < j} \mathbb{I}(T_i < T_j) \cdot \mathbb{I}(\hat{h}_i > \hat{h}_j)}{\sum_{i < j} \mathbb{I}(T_i < T_j)}, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function.

Table 1: C-index Comparison of Proposed Models and Benchmarks

Metric C-index	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Benchmark models	Penalized AG	Elastic Net Cox	RSF
	0.4616	0.6087	0.5305
Unsupervised	NMF+KDE	NMF+Frailty	NMF+SE
	0.5128	0.5419	0.5419
Supervised	PLS+KDE	PLS+Frailty	PLS+SE
	0.5381	0.5511	0.5510

Table 1 summarizes the C-index for all methods. Among the benchmarks, EN-Cox attains the highest score (0.6087), with RSF next (0.5305) and the penalized AG last (0.4616). Introducing unsupervised NMF factors improves over AG: NMF + KDE reaches 0.5128 and adding either a frailty term or a self-exciting component lifts the score to 0.5419. Supervised PLS factors perform even better, the best variant being PLS + Frailty at 0.5511, closely followed by PLS + SE at 0.5510 and PLS + KDE at 0.5381. Although none of the low-rank models surpass EN-Cox, they all exceed the AG baseline and generally outpace RSF.

5.3.2 Integrated Brier Score (IBS)

The Integrated Brier Score (IBS) assesses both discrimination and calibration by measuring the squared difference between actual survival status and predicted survival probabilities over time. The Brier score at time t is:

$$BS(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(I\{T_i > t\} - \hat{S}(t|X_i) \right)^2, \quad \text{where } \hat{S}(t|X_i) = \exp\left(-\int_0^t \hat{h}(u|X_i) du\right). \quad (22)$$

The IBS is then:

$$IBS = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau BS(t) dt, \quad (23)$$

where τ is the maximum observation time. Lower Integrated Brier Score (IBS) denotes better calibration, with values below 0.20 widely regarded as strong performance.

As shown in Table 2, EN-Cox again leads (0.118), well below this threshold. RSF attains 0.207, and the penalized AG lags at 0.361. Among our dimension-reduced variants, NMF+KDE achieves 0.180 and both PLS+KDE and NMF+SE remain under 0.20, all improving substantially on the AG baseline and RSF. Models that append a frailty term perform less well (≈ 0.22), suggesting that the extra stochastic component may add variance without compensating gains in calibration. Overall, the low-rank variants close part of the gap to EN-Cox while remaining simpler and more interpretable than tree ensembles.

Table 2: IBS Comparison of Proposed Models and Benchmarks

Metric IBS	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Benchmark models	Penalized AG 0.3611	Elastic Net Cox 0.1179	RSF 0.2074
Unsupervised	NMF+KDE 0.1795	NMF+Frailty 0.2172	NMF+SE 0.1877
Supervised	PLS+KDE 0.1985	PLS+Frailty 0.2178	PLS+SE 0.2177

5.3.3 Monthly risk map

Figure 6 shows the model’s risk map for April–December 2018. We rank all volcanoes by their predicted eruption probability for this period and display the top decile sites. Each red dot is a volcano, with darker red indicating higher predicted risk. Blue circles mark observed eruptions. Six of the seven events fall on or very near highlighted sites, which shows good recall. Several highlighted sites did not erupt, so false positives are visible; this is expected when we visualize a fixed top fraction rather than choose an operating point for higher precision. We did not perform decision calibration for this figure. In future work we will calibrate on held-out periods using precision–recall or cost-based criteria to control alert volume.

Figure 6: Risk map of April to December 2018

6. Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we investigated the application of survival analysis to the problem of long-term, global volcanic eruption forecasting. To handle the high-dimensional feature space, we adopted the dimension reduction techniques NMF and PLS. Our proposed model shows a slight advantage over some selected baselines and performs reasonably well in situations where high-quality data is limited. The model’s simple structure also makes it adaptable to other spatio-temporal, time-to-event problems. However, while our method shows improvement, the overall performance metrics remain modest, indicating plenty of room for improvement.

One reason for the modest performance may stem from the inherent limitations of our chosen techniques. NMF is primarily effective at capturing linear structures, making it less effective in modeling complex, non-linear dependencies. Its sensitivity to initialization can also lead to inconsistent results. Similarly, PLS is also constrained by its assumption of linear relationships, which may not fully capture the complex interactions present in the data.

Thus, for future work, we have the following plans: first, we plan to explore more advanced feature extraction methods. Word embeddings, for example, allow for a more flexible representation by mapping categorical variables into a continuous low-dimensional space. This could enable the model to capture nonlinear relationships and semantic similarities, though potentially at the cost of reduced interpretability. We will also investigate group lasso for more structured feature selection.

Second, we will evaluate more sophisticated modeling approaches. Our experiments indicated that applying one-hot encoding followed by dimensionality reduction yielded better results than directly using standard tree-based models, contrary to our initial expectations. This outcome may suggest that standard tree models are not well-adapted to recurrent event survival settings. To investigate this further, we plan to evaluate more tailored approaches, such as XGBoost, which are designed to capture complex feature interactions more effectively. To better handle streaming data and improve generalization, we also want to explore online learning frameworks.

Third, our current work involved limited hyperparameter tuning to ensure faster computation. In the future, we plan to find a better balance between convergence speed and performance. We can achieve this by employing more efficient search strategies like Bayesian optimization or by implementing early stopping criteria to prevent unnecessary computation.

In summary, we hope these future efforts will allow for a comprehensive comparison of different alternatives, helping to evaluate the trade-offs among interpretability, flexibility, and predictive accuracy in the critical task of modeling volcanic eruption hazards.

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